

EFFECT OF BRANDING ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR AT VIJAY BHARAT MOTORS PVT LTD, BIDAR

BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA
HOD and ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR
DEPARTMENT OF MBA
LINGARAJ APPA ENGINEERING COLLEGE BIDAR-585403
bhadrappabhavimani@gmail.com
Orcid id-0000-0003-3214-7261

ABSTRACT

The aim of the project is to study about the EFFECT OF BRANDING ON CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF FORD CARS. Now car industry is one of the most competitive industries of the world. So the consumer is also differentiating while purchase. I surveyed that on what points the consumers where differentiating between various Models and Brands of FORD and other competitors. The main motive is to know how brand is effecting on consumer buying behaviour. The study was conducted to determine the level of effect of Branding on consumer buying behaviour to examine interactive roe of those factors that determines brand image and loyalty, to know brand image and loyalty of Ford cars and to suggest measures for developing brand in Bidar district Karnataka state. The data's are collected through questionnaire from a sample of 50 Ford car user They were selected as convenience sampling method.

1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of the study is to understand the structure, significance and implications of brand images of these three largest automobile manufacturers and the seers in the Indian market segment FORD, TOYOTA, HUNDYAI, As well as to form conclusions that would outline the effect of these images on consumer behaviour in Bidar.

The result is clearly identified not only bastion elements of each manufacturers brand image and have categorically manifested the fact that consumer behaviour in the premium segment is predominantly affected by the brand's images of quality ,luxury and style ,but their buying decision are also coordinated gratefully with the perception of given vehicles image by society

The second goal of the study is to draw upon the attained conclusions in in order to be able to potentially relay a certain amount of information to these manufacturers about the exceptional significance of their brand image and suggest possible ways to maintaining and exploiting it to retain current customers and attract new ones.

In today's highly globalized, extremely, dynamic and incredibly rapid moving world, there is an abundance of diversity of products in virtually all market segments and automobile industry marks an overload of manufacturers and model exploiting every possible market

niche in order to accommodate effectively all the possible needs of potential customers. The time tested synergy of technology mechanics and craftsmanship inexhaustible variations of products with remarkable capabilities in different shapes and sizes,

There are myriad of different opinion and attempts to provide a logical explanation absolute and unshakeable dominance of Ford, Hyundai and Toyota and comparing other luxury cars BMW, Audi and Mercedes Benz. are the premium segment in the automobile industry, ranging from statement about their mechanical and technical innovation and superiority to description of their heritage and History. However there is reason to believe that while all these theories are valid, the truth lies elsewhere. A large number of other brands offer vehicles with matching, if not superior bends of mechanical durability and technological refinement while also being able to exhibit rivalling history .

The study will follow the supposition that the effect of Brands soft skills, namely their brand images, and prices is the most influential factor in swaying the customer's buying behaviour in favour.

According to ford manufacturers product or equipment are manufactured for buyers and buyers are those who buy different products according to their needs. They buy those products in order to satisfy their needs and wants. Consumer buying decision a process that involves differenet steps like the recognition of need, search for the information, evaluation of alternatives, selection and in the last post purchase behaviour. There are lots of factors which effect the consumer behaviour and those factors lead him towards purchasing. In this research we will see the Impact of Branding on consumer buying behaviour means the factor of consumer behaviour helps him to choose a particular Brand accourding to his need and choice.leads the entire world to become one market. Whole world lead to Becoming single Universal community to serve different cultures. With the increase in global competition, the company's focus to serve local market has find themselves at a disadvantage and loosing competitive edge that they so much strived to achieve. This all led to decline the important in national borders and more emphasis on what the consumers actually demand. From buyers point of view,the reaction toward global Brand seems differently among different people. On one hand buyers apprise global brands as their status symbol and on other hand globally known brands are criticized to threatening national customs by imposing their culture that's lead to loss of culture identity.

O'cass said that due to the Globalization, competition is increased and every time innovation is needed for making the brand globally known and for maintaining their status. For every brand to be successful, brand identity and recognition is very important. Now people perceive the brand as their recognition, achivment and status symbol.

And other hand woods explained that consumers are emotionally attached to different brand is favourite celebrity of a consumer. He will buy that product because if he will also want to look like his favourite personality.

So celebrity branding is basically leads to arousal of emotional and we can say that branding influence that behaviour of consumers and consumers behave in response according to

various dimension of consumer behaviour which influence them in selecting a branded product and impact of brands on consumer behaviour. We will try to explicit the relationship between branding and consumer buying behaviour.

Organizations start to do business in order to gain money in terms of profitability which is exceed of income then their expenses utilize in the business when organization start business they think for the whole scenario of consumer.

Purchase behaviour with intention to gain more income and growth than the competitors so they create a long term bond with consumers in the shape of brands that will take the organization towards success and heigher profit margins also results in strong market position.

People perceive the brands differently according to their preferences and sometimes may be depends on past experiences and their decisions are directly or indirectly related to these perspectives.

It is said that consumers behaviour towards branded products or services according to their age, gender and personality traits and people get social according to their personality traits. The research explicated that individuals behave differently towards the same brand according to their gender. So gender is the basis of determining the consumer behaviour.

Brands are mostly used by rich females to show their wealth and high class status. It is a trend in India due to the increasing number of brands and fashion that if you are rich, you cannot buy the unbranded products . So it is further argued that status consumption and conspicuous consumption are related to each other and status consumption is the reason of conspicuous consumption.

1.2 INDUSTRY PROFILE

FOR MOTOR COMPANY, Commonly known as Ford, is an American multinational auto maker that has its main headquarters in Dearborn, Michigan, a suburb of Detroit. It was founded by Henry Ford and incorporated on 16 June 1903. The company sells automobiles and commercial vehicles under the Ford brand, and most luxury cars under the Lincoln brand. Ford also owns Brazilian SUV manufacturer Troller, an 8% stake in Aston Martin of United Kingdom and a 32% stake in Jiangling motors. It also has joint-venture in Changan (Changan Ford), Taiwan (Ford Lioho), Thailand(Auto Alliance Thailand),Turkey (Ford Otosan), and Russia (Ford Sollers). The Company is listed on the New York Stock Exchange and is controlled by the Ford Family. They have minority ownership but the majority of the voting power.

The largest family-controlled company in the world, the Ford motor company has been in continuous family control for over 110 years. Ford now encompasses two brands ; ford and Lincoln. Ford once owned 5 other luxury brands; Volvo, Land Rover, Jaguar, Aston Martin and Mercury Over time, those brands were sold to other companies and mercury was discontinued.

FOUNDATION:

Henry Ford built his first automobile, which he called a quadricycle, at his home in Detroit in 1896. The location has been redeveloped, where the Michigan Building now stands, and tracks for the Detroit people mover and the Times Square people mover station are nearby. At the entrance to the Michigan Building, there is a commemorative plaque identifying the original location of the Ford home. The coal shed has been recreated using the original bricks at Greenfield Village in nearby Dearborn. His initial foray into automobile manufacturing was the Detroit Automobile Company, founded in 1899. The company founded in 1901 was recognized as the Henry Ford Company in March 1902, after falling out with his financial backers, Ford left the company with the right to his name and 900 Dollars.

Henry Ford turned to an acquaintance, coal dealer Alexander Y. Malcomson, to help finance another automobile company. Malcomson put up the money to start the partnership. "Ford and Malcomson" and the pair designed a car and began ordering parts. However, by February 1903, Ford and Malcomson had gone through more money than expected, and the manufacturing firm of John and Horace Dodge, who had made parts for Ford and Malcomson, was demanding payment. Malcomson, constrained by his coal business

Demands, turned to his uncle John S. Gray, the president at the German-American Savings Bank and a good friend. Malcomson proposed incorporating Ford and Malcomson to bring in new investors, and wanted Gray to join the company, thinking that Gray's name would attract other investors. Gray was not interested at first, but Malcomson promised he could withdraw his share at any time, so Gray reluctantly agreed on the strength of Gray's name, Malcomson recruited other business acquaintances to invest, including local merchants Albert Strelow and Vernon Fry, lawyers John Anderson and Horace Rackham, Charles T. Bennett of the Daisy Air Rifle Company and his own clerk James Couzens. Malcomson also convinced the Dodges to accept stock in lieu of payment.

On June 16, 1903, the Ford Motor Company was incorporated, with 12 investors owning a total of 1000 shares. Ford and Malcomson together retained 51% of the new company in exchange for their earlier investments. When the total stock ownership was tabulated, shares in the company were: Henry Ford (255 Shares), John S. Gray (105 Shares), John W. Anderson (50 Shares), Horace Rackham (50 Shares), Horace E. Dodge (50 Shares), John F. Dodge (50 Shares), Charles T. Bennett (50 Shares), Vernon C. Fry (50 Shares), Albert Strelow (50 Shares), James Couzens (25 Shares), Charles J. Woodall (10 Shares).

At the 1st stockholder meeting held June 18, Gray was elected President, Ford Vice President and James Couzens Secretary despite Gray's misgivings. The Ford Motor Company was immediately profitable with profits by October 1, 1903 of almost \$37,000. A dividend of 10% was paid that October, an additional dividend of 20% at the beginning of 1904, and another 68% in June 1904. Two dividends of 100% each in June and July 1905 brought the total investors' profits to nearly 300% in just over 2 years, 1905 total profit was almost \$300,000.

FORD INDIA PRIVATE LIMITED:

Ford India Private Limited is a collaboration between Ford Motor Company, a share of 49% and 51% of share of Mahindra and Mahindra company. Ford India private Limited Head Quarters are in Maraimalai Nagar, Chennai, Tamil Nadu. It currently is the sixth largest car maker in India after Maruti Suzuki, Hyundai, Honda, Tata and Mahindra.

1.3 COMPANY PROFILE:

Ford manufactures and export vehicles and engines made at its integrated manufacturing facilities in Chennai, Tamil Nadu and Sanand, Gujarat. Since its entry in India in 1995, Ford has invested more than US\$ 2 billion to expand its manufacturing facilities and sales & service footprint to meet demand in one of the world's fastest-growing auto markets. Ford India's integrated manufacturing facility at Maraimalai Nagar, near Chennai, produces its award-winning range of products including the Ford export and ford endeavour. As part of its overall commitment, Ford inaugurated its US\$ 1 billion state-of-the-art integrated manufacturing facility in Sanand, Gujarat in March 2015. With Sanand being operational, Ford India has doubled its annual installed manufacturing capacity to 610,000 engines and 440,000 vehicles. The sub-four-metre compact sedan, Ford Figo Aspire, became the first car to roll out from the new Ford Sanand plant. The plant also manufactures new Figo hatchback.

Ford's biggest-ever product line-up in India today offers a vehicle to suit the needs of nearly every consumer. In 2016, Ford has also given Indian consumers their first opportunity to own the iconic Ford Mustang. Debuting ahead of the Delhi Auto Expo 2016 and set to hit Indian showrooms later this year, the new Mustang is all set to bring the world-class performance and refinement of Ford's iconic pony car to Indian's roads. As part of its strategy to Make in India for India and the World, Ford continues to strengthen India as a center of excellence for small cars and low displacement engines. The company has embarked on an accelerated export strategy and presently, exports Figo, Aspire, and EcoSport to over 40 markets around the world.

Along with introducing new products, Ford continues to grow closer to customers with the continued expansion of its nationwide dealership network as well as world-class after-sales offerings. Presently, Ford has more than 376 sales and service outlets in 209 cities across India. To enhance affordability and accessibility, Ford has introduced many pioneering initiatives that reduce the cost of ownership including the Sub-assembly of parts, Pan-India Roadside Assistance, and Mobile Service Support. To ensure total transparency in service costs, Ford also introduced a unique Service Price Promise, which allows customers to calculate the vehicles' periodic maintenance costs even before booking the service at the dealership. Ensuring customer convenience, Ford has expanded the availability of Ford Genuine Parts with the appointment of distributors in Maharashtra, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Delhi, Tamil Nadu, AP, and Telangana.

Ford's presence in India includes Ford Credit India, which started dealer wholesale inventory and retail financing in 2015 as a non-banking financial company. With five decades of global experience, Ford Credit's operations span in as many as 100 countries where it has emerged

as a preferred automotive financier for both Ford customers as well as dealers. Ford Credit is known for its reliable and transparent loan products at competitive rates, flexible terms, and outstanding customer service. Continuing to generate employment and help the economy, Ford's operations currently employ more than 14,000 hard-working, dedicated men and women across its operations in India which also include Global Business Services, with offices in Chennai, New Delhi, and Coimbatore.

Registered as Ford Motor Pvt Ltd. (FMPL) as a legal entity, Global Business Services provide innovative solutions to nearly every Ford locations around the world in areas of Information Technology, Product Engineering, Finance and Accounting, Automotive Financing, Material, Planning & Logistics, Marketing Sales and Service, Analytics, and Purchasing. Driving innovation from India, Ford recently announced plans to build a new global engineering and technology center in Chennai. Besides the establishment of a global engineering and technology center, the new Ford campus spread across 28 acres will host operations of Ford Global Business Services in areas of IT, Product Engineering, Finance and Accounting, data analysis, manufacturing among others. Ford's commitment to India is not just business centric. At the heart of our business plans are people and communities. Going further with its Better World philosophy, Ford India in association with Ford Motor Company Fund announced 'Operation Better World,' with the endeavour to address issues related to Education, Sustainability and Auto Safety around Communities where it operates.

The address of this outlet is DN 19/4/3391/1, Humnabad Rd, Naubad, Bidar, Karnataka - 585403.

1.4 FIANACIAL STATEMENT

Particulars	31-12-2019	31-12-2018	31-12-2017	31-12-2016	31-12-2015
Cash on Hand	34,651	33,951	38,927	38,827	35,176
Notes and Loans Receivable	53,651	54,353	52,210	46,266	45,137
Inventory	10,786	11,220	11,176	8,898	8,319
Other Current Assets	5,722	3,930	3,889	3,368	2,913
Total Current Assets	114,047	114,649	116,801	108,461	102,587
Property, Plant, and Equipment	36,469	36,178	35,327	32,072	30,163
Long-Term Investment	31,749	31,828	31,320	32,133	30,317
Goodwill and Intangible Assets					
Other Long- Term	10,706	7,929	8,104	5,656	4,795

Assets					
Total Long-Term Assets	144,490	141,891	141,695	129,490	122,338
Total Assets	258,537	256,540	258,496	237,951	224,925
Total Current Liabilities	98,132	95,569	94,600	90,281	82,336
Long Term Debt	101,361	100,720	102,666	93,301	89,879
Other Non-Current Liabilities	25,324	23,588	24,711	24,395	23,457
Total Long- Term Liabilities	127,175	125,005	128,290	118,483	113,932
Total Liabilities	225,307	220,574	222,890	208,764	196,268
Common Stock Net	41	41	41	41	41
Retained Earnings (Accumulated Deficit)	20,320	22,668	21,906	15,634	14,414
Comprehensive Income	7,728	7,366	6,959	7,013	6,257
Other Share Holders Equity					
Share Holder Equity	33,230	35,966	35,606	29,187	28,657
Total Liabilities and Share Holders Equity	258,537	256,540	258,496	234,951	224,925

CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Meaning:

Branding is a marketing practice in which a company creates a name, symbol or design that is easily identifiable as belonging to the company.

This helps to identify a products and distinguish it from other products and services.

Definition:

According to Philip cottler “ Brand is a name, sign, symbol or design or a combination of these included to identify the goods of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiable them from of competitors”.

Branding is the process of creating a strong, positive perception of your company and it’s products in your customers mind.

Branding is a seller's promise to deliver a specific set of features, benefits, and services consistent to the buyers.

Importance of Branding:

- ❖ Consumer side:
 - Identification of matter of the product.
 - Risk reducer.
 - Search cost reducer.
 - Symbol of
 - Symbolic devices that allow customers to represent their values and images.
- ❖ Manufacturer side:
 - Valuable asset.
 - Signal of satisfied customers and quality.
 - Premium process.
 - Sustainable sales and profit.
 - Financial returns.
 - Competitive advantage.

Significance / Advantages of Branding:

- ◆ Easy to Advertise
- ◆ Easy to identify the products
- ◆ Creation of separate market
- ◆ To get more price
- ◆ Provide good reputation
- ◆ Increase business value
- ◆ Helps in facing competition
- ◆ Acquires customer easily

Disadvantages:

- ◆ Loss of control
- ◆ Risk of brand equity dilution
- ◆ Negative feedback effects
- ◆ Lack of brand focus
- ◆ Organisational direction

Role of Brand:

- Brand helps in identification of sources of product.
- Brand assigns the responsibility to product marketer,
- It reduces search cost.
- It gives promise brand with maker of product.
- It is a symbolic device.
- It is a single of quality.

Nature of Branding on consumer buying behaviour

How individual customers, groups, organisations, select, buy, use and dispose, ideas, goods and services to satisfy their needs and wants.

1. Target Ability:

One of the main characteristics of brands is that they must be targetable.

2. Awareness:

Another characteristics of brand is that it creates awareness. Brand awareness is the percentage of people who are aware of a particular brand,

There are many ways to build brand awareness including television, radio, magazines, newspaper and internet advertising logos also helps companies build brand awareness.

3. Consistency:

Brand must also remain consistent through their existence. Business make numerous promises in commercials and ads about their brands and consumers expect companies to continue living up to these promises.

4. Distinctive Design:

People make a decision about the company and the brand within a few seconds of initial contact so first impression do count.

5. Loyalty:

Brand loyalty is the highest achievement or apex for any company.

Brand loyalists are customers who buy a particular brand exclusively.

2.2 LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Aaker (1991)

He defines in his study the conceptual framework develops is useful for examining the contribution of brand association, brand awareness, perceived develops is useful for examining the contribution of brand association, brand awareness, perceived value and brand loyalty to brand equity.

2. Thomas Semon (1993)

In his research he suggests the inclusion of brand loyalty and response style in customers satisfaction. The author suggest that many of the brand switch triggers are based on communications rather than personal experience.

3. Kent and Allen (1994)

The study focused on brand familiarity's role in increasing ad memorability and moderating competitive interference. Their findings suggest that established brands have important advantages in advertising, consumers would be more likely to recall ad information and their memory should be less affected by exposure to competitors.

4. Chaudhri and Holbrook (2001)

The aims of the study are to review the dimensions of customer based brand equity by drawing together strands from various literature and empirical studies made within the area of customer based brand equity. A conceptual framework for measuring customer based brand equity is developed to provide a more integrative conceptualization of brand equity.

5. Gil Bashe (2001)

The report is on the efforts of pharmaceutical executive to focus on consumers needs, value of customer relationship management, significance of integrating a brand emotion ingredient in a marketing strategy, challenge of maximizing total brand assets and elements of successful marketing and sales campaigns.

6. Romaniuk and Sharp (2003)

in his study he tested three hypotheses about the relationship between brand perception and loyalty. They found a. there was little evidence that any particular attributes are more related to customer loyalty than other nor b. that there were specific brand positions that were uniquely associated with higher loyalty.

7. Ayanwale (2005)

He described that when there is number of rivals and customers have changed brand selections producers wants to understand the features that can advantage the attraction of purchasers. Man and woman both similarly influenced by promotion for brand selections.

8. Kevin (2005)

He focuses on the use of effective advertising to create an equity position in the marketplace. The author concludes by saying that effective advertising can be a powerful part of a company's marketing plan, and it is an important investment in the company.

9. Tam (2007)

He said that brand use as valuable asset and attractive trick to capture consumers for specific goods. Customer behaviour can be inspected on the base of brand consciousness, relationship and loyalty.

10. Khasawneh and Hasouneh (2010)

He stated that customers recognize the reputation of brand while in their buying decisions and customers demographic features have no significant relation and influence on brand awareness.

11. Nepalia (2011)

Summed up that accomplish the brand means to apply marketing tackles for particular goods. If brand will be managed effectively product value and brand loyalty will also be enhanced in customers mind.

12. Y.L Fayrene Chieng, Lee Chai Goi (2011)

In his studies the customer based brand equity is evaluating the consumer response to brand name. the consumer based brand equity is an asset of four dimensions that are brand awareness. Brand loyalty the consumers perception of the overall superiority of a product caring that brand name when compared to other brands.

13. Shobha et al. (2011)

In their study discussed about brand extension concept and its acceptance with consumers. Result of the study indicates that attitude toward the parent brand is the strongest factor influencing extension evaluation, substantiating the efficacy of extension.

14. Akhlagh and abadi (2012)

He said that brand is important tool that helps out to corporation to receive a competitive advantage. Brand strength is multidimensional structure with customer opinion. Brand assets with distinguish quality and rate of dairy goods have a progressive and direct link with customer purchasing behaviour.

15. Doostar (2012)

He said that brand fairness has a positive impact on buying decision, customers feel by heights of brand equity for the first time after use and then tend to make buying decisions, they use brands that is slightly aware with its name and express value that this worth has made for them.

16. Akhlagh and Abadi (2012)

He said that helps out to corporations to receive a competitive advantage. Brand strength is multidimensional structure with customer opinion. Brand assets with distinguish quality and rate of dairy goods have a progressive and direct link with customer purchasing behaviour.

17. Malik (2013)

He mentioned that brand image has solid progressive control on customer purchasing behaviour as it's an implied method that can modify people's purchasing behaviours positively and youngsters in Gujranwala are becoming more attentive for brand named goods to show off their character sign.

18. Zhang YI (2015)

He said that here brand equity which refers to the consumers general perception and feeling about the brand and has an influence on the consumer behaviour. The most

studies measure brand equity from perspective of consumer or from the company itself.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Competition is very high in today's marketplace. Every organisation is therefore determined to differentiate their brands and service offerings compared to their competitors. In effect, everybody is trying to have unique features in their brand and market them. If organisations want to succeed in this space, they need to assess their brands honestly else similar me-too brands are out there in the market which can destroy their entire marketing efforts. Branding suffering from symmetry syndrome will find it difficult to survive in the market after some time.

No market manager would like their brand to be seen as a commodity. In fact the whole concept of marketing is based on selling the brand which can be differentiable. It is generally argued that goods and services are differentiable. Few argue that this is applied only to consumer goods however in industrial goods and services, they can be distinguished.

3.2 NEED OF THE STUDY

In the marketplace, differentiation is the key. Any market be it a producer, intermediary, seller or an agent consistency tries to offer something different than what is being offered in the market.

The usual opinions about commodities are that they are highly price sensitive. A little lower the sales. In ideal economics world, the price volume sensitivity exists. However this hardly happens. In the real world, there are other factors apart from price which can impact sales.

With a brand uniqueness measurement tool at their disposal, the brand managers can know how their brands are performing in the marketplace.

3.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyse the industry overview of life insurance and oral care sectors of India.
- To analyse the brand positioning strategies of leading brands of the country and understand the communication dynamics.
- To understand review and define the attributes for "Brand Success".
- To develop the concept and algorithm related to brand symmetry index. Use the algorithm to develop the best model fit to measure brand symmetry index and interpret the results.

3.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- The study covers the users of ford cars.
- The study included users of ford car in bidar district.
- The study is detailed about effect of branding on consumer buying behaviour.
- Study includes brand and brand impact on india consumer behaviour and bidar citizens.

3.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the strategy for a study and the plan by which the strategy is to be carried out. It specifies the methods and procedure for the collection, measurement, analysis of data. For the purpose of this research design has been described below

Data collection:

Data collection is one of the method of the information from different sources.

Method of data collection:

The method of data collection are of two types and they are primary data and secondary data

Primary data:

Primary data collection is first and basic method ,which is used to collect initial material during the research process,

Secondary data:

Secondary data means those data which are already available that is the data which has been already collection and analyzed by someone else. These data can be collected from books, office journals, reports and company policies.

4.DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 From which sources you got aware about ford.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Newspaper Advertisement	15	30%
2	Experienced user	10	20%
3	Event and promotion	12	24%
4	TV Advertisement	08	16%
5	Online Source	05	10%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph we can show that among 50 customers, 30% customers are aware by news paper advertisement, 20% are experienced user, 24% are aware by event and promotion, 16% is tv and advertisement, and only 10% by online source aware about the having ford cars.

4.2 Have been you using any car or ford before.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Yes	30	60%
2	No	20	40%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph 60% of people were used cars weather that may be some other and only 40% were using the same brand or only ford.

4.3 What is the daily travelling kilometre per day.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Less than 30	25	50%
2	31 – 60	15	30%
3	Above 61	10	20%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph we know daily how much people be attached by using the cars according to this chart 50% of people runs less than 30 km/day, 31 to 60 is 30% and above 61 is that 20% only.

4.4 What other factors influence more to buy ford car.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of respondents
1	Nearby showroom	20	40%
2	Availability of spares	7	14%
3	Availability of model	7	14%
4	Product performance	6	12%
5	Brand image	10	20%

Total		50	100%
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Interpretation:

The graph shows that the 40% people are influenced to buy ford because of nearby showroom, the 14% of people to buy a ford vehicle because of availability of spares, and availability of model 14% are influenced, 12% of product performance, and 20% of people are influenced on brand image.

4.5 How far celebrity endorsement influenced your buying decisions.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	High influence	20	40%
2	Normal influence	10	20%
3	Not influence	7	14%
4	Less influence	7	14%

5	Natural	6	12%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

The graph shows that in the present area 40% people are high influenced by celebrity endorsement and 20% normal influenced, 14% is not influenced and 14% are less influenced and 12% are natural.

4.6 Does financing influence your buying decisions.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	High influence	25	50%
2	Less influence	15	30%
3	Normal influence	7	14%
4	Not influence	3	6%

Total		50	100%
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Interpretation:

The graph says that how financing influence buying decisions. High influenced are 50%, 30% are less influenced 14% are normal influenced and 6% are not influenced.

4.7 Past experience with other ford services if any

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Good	20	40%
2	Average	15	30%
3	poor	15	30%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph 40% of people were told good and 30% people average and 30% of people were poor.

4.8 Brand has now become a status symbol do you agree.

SI. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Strongly agree	20	40%
2	Agree	15	30%
3	Natural	5	10%
4	Strongly disagree	4	8%

5	Disagree	6	12%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In the graph mentioned that 40% of people are strongly agree , 30% of people only agree and 10% are natural, 8% of people are strongly disagree and 12% are disagree.

4.9 Do you think focus on branding while purchasing is correct.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Yes	25	50%
2	No	15	30%
3	Not sure	10	20%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph focusing on branding while purchasing the 50% of people are say yes and 30% of people are no and remaining 20% of people are not sure.

4.10 Who influence you to purchase the brand.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Family	10	20%
2	Friends	15	30%
3	Advertisement	20	40%
4	Self	5	10%

Total		50	100%
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Interpretation:

That graph says that only 20% of people are influenced by family, and friends 30%, by advertisement 40%, and by self 10%.

4.11 Motivation factor in decision making process of purchasing a brand product.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Quality	23	46%
2	Price	15	30%
3	Packaging	5	10%

4	Tradition	7	14%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph indicates 40% of people are motivated by its quality and 30% on price, 10% on packaging, and 14% in tradition.

4.12 Would you recommend ford cars to others.

SI. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Yes	35	70%
2	No	15	30%

Total		50	100
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Interpretation:

The graph shows that 70% of people recommended by ford cars to other and only 30% are says no.

4.13 What aged groups are user of brand products.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	14 – 30	20	40%
2	31 – 40	15	30%

3	41 – 50	10	20%
4	51 - 60	5	10%
Total		52	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph we can say that 40% are agreed to user of branded products between (14 to 30) and 30% are (31 to 40), 20% are (41 to 50) and (51 to 60) are 10%.

4.14 Do you think ford car has any negative about spares.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Yes	15	30%

2	No	35	70%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

This graph shows that 70% of people say no, and 30% of people are negative about spares.

4.15 How much you trust on Bhart Ford Bidar.

SI. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	10%	5	10%

2	25%	08	16%
3	50%	12	24%
4	75%	15	30%
5	100%	10	20%
Total		50	100%

Interpretation:

In this graph stated that among 50 respondents based on percentage to 100% the only 20% are trusted on bhart ford bidar.

5.1 FINDINGS:

- The both male and female respondents are used to prefer the branded products and of ford endover.
- The every age group of respondents is prefer to fuel consumption and followed by others.
- The majority of respondents used to prefer status symbol.
- The majority of respondents is yearly income of Rs.4 lakhs to 6lakhs and above 6lakhs is prefer to status symbol.

- The majority of the respondents are preferred to over performance of ford figo as normal and good.
- Most of the respondents have got positive response from the company.
- Most of the respondents have fully satisfied by the ford car.
- Majority of the employees have got job satisfaction.
- Majority of the respondents have got well experienced of ford
- Majority of respondents have satisfied with Vijay Bhart ford Bidar showroom / dealer.
- Majority of respondents have good relationship with the showroom.
- Majority of respondents are more user of branded vehicles.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS:

- The both male and female respondents have preferred to use may people of ford cars specially ford figo and endover.
- By the study both male and female suggested that to improve sales / services.
- The majority of people are advice to bring showroom No. 1 in the district.
- The majority of respondents are preferred to buy all colour of ford cars and all are well designed.
- The majority of respondents are suggested to bring long term instalments to preferred to buy.

6.CONCLUSION:

The study makes us to know the understand the brand that is successful in the market place in bidar district it is able to convince the user about the used model of “Ford “ cars. The questionnaire was prepared through the inputs taken from the past researchers and also from the feedback from the respondents. In today's automatized world many people are preferred to use branded products, from lower level to the top level. According to many view branding teaches us to live life respectfully and feels occurs grateness and branding can change person life after this study I came to know that brand can change the persons behaviour life style.

REFERENCES

1. BHADRAPP A HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , PERFORMANCE AFFECTING FACTORS OF INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS, George Washington International Law Review, Vol.- 07 Issue -01, April-June 2021, PAGE No : 607-621, Available at: <http://archive-gwilr.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Bhadrapa-Haralayya.pdf>

2. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL , IMPLICATIONS OF BANKING SECTOR ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA, flusserstudies, Volume 30, June 2021,Page No:1068-1080, Available at: <https://flusserstudies.org/archives/801>
3. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , P.S.AITHAL ,STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF BANKS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRY, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com) ,Volume: 2, Issue: 5, May 2021, Page No : 184-194. Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2105025.pdf>
4. Bhadrappa Haralayya ; P. S. Aithal . "Study on Model and Camel Analysis of Banking" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals ,Volume 4 ,Issue 11 ,May 2021 Page 244-259. Available at <https://irejournals.com/paper-details/1702750>
5. B. Haralayya and P. S. Aithal, “A Study On Structure and Growth of Banking Industry in India”, International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management ,Volume 4, Issue 5, May 2021. Page no 225–230. Available at: <https://www.journals.resaim.com/ijresm/article/view/778/749>.
6. Bhadrappa Haralayya, Retail Banking Trends in India ,International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods (IJARESM), Volume: 9, Issue: 5, Year: May 2021, Page No : 3730-3732. Available At http://www.ijaresm.com/uploaded_files/document_file/Bhadrappa_Haralayyaqscw.pdf
7. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, FACTORS DETERMINING THE EFFICIENCY IN INDIAN BANKING SECTOR : A TOBIT REGRESSION ANALYSIS", International Journal of Science & Engineering Development Research (www.ijedr.org), Vol.6, Issue 6, June-2021, page no.1 - 6, , Available :<http://www.ijedr.org/papers/IJSDR2106001.pdf>
8. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, STUDY ON PRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS, International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology, Volume 8, Issue 1, June-2021 ,Page no: 159 – 164, Available: http://ijirt.org/master/publishedpaper/IJIRT151514_PAPER.pdf
9. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA , STUDY OF BANKING SERVICES PROVIDED BY BANKS IN INDIA, International Research Journal of Humanities and Interdisciplinary Studies (www.irjhis.com), Volume: 2, Issue: 6, Year: June 2021,Page No : 06-12, Available at : <http://irjhis.com/paper/IRJHIS2106002.pdf>.
10. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANK PERFORMANCE

- USING CAMEL APPROACH", International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (www.jetir.org | UGC and issn Approved), Vol.8, Issue 5, May-2021, page no 305-314, Available at : <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2105840.pdf>
11. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, ANALYSIS OF BANK PRODUCTIVITY USING PANEL CAUSALITY TEST, Journal of Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Volume 50, Issue 6, June-2021 , Page no: 1 – 16, Available at: <https://app.box.com/s/o71lh776opeypauvzucp9esntjwur9zf>
 12. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL, INTER BANK ANALYSIS OF COST EFFICIENCY USING MEAN, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJIRSET), Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021 ,Page no: 6391-6397, Available at: http://www.ijirset.com/upload/2021/june/97_INTER_NC1.pdf
 13. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY AND PROFITABILITY MATRIX OF BANKS BY HMTFP AND FPTFP, Science, Technology and Development Journal, Volume 10, Issue 6, June-2021, Page no: 190-203, Available at: <http://journalstd.com/gallery/23-june2021.pdf>
 14. BHADRAPPA HARALAYYA, P.S.AITHAL , ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY BY AGGREGATE LEVEL, Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology, Volume 13, Issue 6, June- 2021 ,Page no: 296-314, available at: <https://www.xajzkjdx.cn/gallery/28-june2021.pdf>
 15. Bhadrappa Haralayya, P S Aithal, "ANALYSIS OF BANKS TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY BY DISAGGREGATE LEVEL", International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT), Volume.9, Issue 6, June 2021, pp.b488-b502, Available at :<http://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2106187.pdf>
 16. Haralayya B. Importance of CRM in Banking and Financial Sectors Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021, 6(1): 8-9
 17. Haralayya B. How Digital Banking has Brought Innovative Products and Services to India. Journal of Advanced Research in Quality Control and Management 2021; 6(1): 16-18
 18. Haralayya B. Top 5 Priorities That will Shape The Future of Retail Banking Industry in India. Journal of Advanced Research in HR and Organizational Management 2021; 8(1&2): 17-18.
 19. Haralayya B. Millennials and Mobile-Savvy Consumers are Driving a Huge Shift in The Retail Banking Industry. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 17-19

20. Haralayya B. Core Banking Technology and Its Top 6 Implementation Challenges. Journal of Advanced Research in Operational and Marketing Management 2021; 4(1): 25-27
21. Nitesh S Vibhute ; Dr. Chandrakant B. Jewargi ; Dr. Bhadrappa Haralayya . "Study on Non-Performing Assets of Public Sector Banks" Iconic Research And Engineering Journals Volume 4, Issue, 12 June 2021, Page 52-61 Available at <https://irejournals.com/formatedpaper/1702767.pdf>
22. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa and Saini, Shrawan Kumar, An Overview on Productive Efficiency of Banks & Financial Institution (2018). International Journal of Research, Volume 05 Issue 12, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837503>
23. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Review on the Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country (2018). Journal for Studies in Management and Planning, Volume 04 Issue 05, April 2018, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837496>
24. Basha, Jeelan and Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Performance Analysis of Financial Ratios - Indian Public Non-Life Insurance Sector (April 30, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3837465>.
25. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, The Productive Efficiency of Banks in Developing Country With Special Reference to Banks & Financial Institution (april 30, 2019). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844432> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844432>
26. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, Study on Performance of Foreign Banks in India (APRIL 2, 2016). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844403> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844403>
27. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-Finance and the Financial Services Industry (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844405> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844405>
28. Haralayya, Dr. Bhadrappa, E-payment - An Overview (MARCH 28, 2014). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3844409> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3844409> .

WEBSITES

- www.fordindiaprivateLtd.com
- www.google.com
- www.Ford.com
- www.luxurycars.in
- Denmark, J. R. (2010). Corporate branding
- Creswell, J.W. (2003). Research design

